

Design and validation of a vacuum chuck for ultra-precision diamond turning of Cu-OFE discs

TSOGO Enzo
CERN, Geneva, Switzerland
enzo-tsogo@outlook.fr

Abstract

This article describes the design, manufacture and experimental validation of a vacuum chuck dedicated to machining high-purity copper discs for CERN's AWAKE project. These discs, components of 12 GHz accelerator cavities, require extreme tolerances in terms of flatness ($< 2 \mu\text{m}$) and roughness ($R_a < 25 \text{ nm}$), ruling out any conventional mechanical chuck because of the induced deformations. A one-piece vacuum chuck was therefore developed, providing effective vacuum clamping while ensuring the coaxiality required for high-precision machining. This system has made it possible to eliminate deformations linked to clamping, which are responsible for 80% of non-conformities in the manufacture of discs. The study included theoretical modelling of vacuum clamping, numerical simulations using ANSYS, and experimental validation of the system mounted on a HEMBRUG Mikrotorn 100 lathe. The results confirm an effective clamping force of 248 N for a vacuum of 70 mbar, giving a safety factor of 13.4 with respect to the forces applied during the finishing operation. This solution has the potential to be integrated into other demanding applications.

1. Introduction

CERN's AWAKE project is part of an effort to reduce the size of accelerators by exploiting the plasma wake field. In 2022, the EN-MME department produced the first prototypes of the AWAKE project's 12 GHz accelerator cavities (Fig. 1.a), which incorporate Cu-OFE (99.99% purity) discs (Fig. 1.b) machined with extreme tolerances. Finishing machining is carried out on a HEMBRUG Mikrotorn 100 lathe, capable of achieving $R_a 0.008 \mu\text{m}$ with diamond tools [1]. However, the current clamping via a three-jaw chuck generates significant post-machining deformations, rendering 80% of the parts non-compliant (Fig. 1.c).

Faced with this problem, a new jawless clamping system was designed: a vacuum chuck adapted to the dynamic constraints of turning. This work presents the development stages, from theoretical foundations to experimental validation.

2. System development

2.1 Principles of vacuum clamping

Pressure is a force applied to a surface, expressed in pascals (Pa) in the International System. The relationship $P = \frac{F}{S}$ is therefore central to this study, with P the pressure, F the force and S the surface. At CERN, atmospheric pressure is approximately 96,392 Pa (or 963.92 mbar).

The operating principle of a vacuum chuck is based on the use of atmospheric pressure as a source of mechanical

energy [2]. By creating a vacuum, a clamping force is generated due to the pressure difference between the inside and the outside, which pushes the part against the support surface, holding it in place. This force acts normally to the surface, but the key factor is the tangential force, to prevent slipping. We therefore apply Coulomb's law of friction [3], according to which:

$$\text{Friction force } F_F = \text{Normal force } F_N * \mu_S$$

with μ_S the coefficient of static friction.

For the vacuum to be effective, the vacuum zone must be sealed, often by O-rings [4].

2.2 Preliminary design calculations

During the machining operation, various forces are applied to the workpiece. This study considers the weight of the workpiece, its inertia during spindle acceleration, the centrifugal force during rotation and the cutting force for finishing with a diamond tool. Theoretical calculations suggest that the sum of the forces to be compensated is 8.29 N. Assuming a static friction coefficient $\mu_S = 0.45$ (machined aluminium/copper), a minimum normal force of 18.4 N is required. With a theoretically useful surface area of $4,312 \text{ mm}^2$, a pressure of 921 mbar (which corresponds to 96% of P_{atm}) would be sufficient to maintain adhesion.

Fig. 1. Initial part tolerancing issue. a) Prototype 12 GHz AWAKE cavity. b) OFE copper disc. c) Flatness defects on one of the 2022 discs

2.3 Transmission of vacuum in rotation

It was then necessary to ensure that this vacuum could be maintained while ensuring that the spindle rotated at the optimum speed for machining.

A pneumatic rotary connector is fitted as standard on the lathe, initially designed to transmit a pressure of 6 bar to feed a PML-PAL pneumatic chuck [5]. The aim was therefore to determine the component's ability to transmit vacuum pressure at different speeds of rotation. Three obturators were designed and manufactured for the spindle nose ducts, incorporating O-rings, Fig. 2.a. On the other side of the coupling, a mounting allows the pneumatic hoses entering the coupling to be connected to the vacuum unit, incorporating a vacuum gauge, Fig. 2.b.

Readings of the minimum stable pressure (maintained over 10 minutes, because one face finishing takes 8 minutes) for the different speeds of rotation demonstrated the ability of the fitting to transmit a vacuum of 70 mbar. On the theoretical clamping surface of the part, this corresponds to a potential clamping force of 385 N. The component can therefore be used in our system.

2.4 Chuck design

Three configurations were studied: a universal chuck with "spider grid" type grooves (Fig. 3.a), a universal plate topped by a dedicated clamping plate (Fig. 3.b), and a made-to-measure one-piece chuck (Fig. 3.c).

The latter choice, although not reusable for other geometries, guarantees the best rigidity and positioning accuracy [6]. It is made from EN AW-6082 aluminium. Vacuum is transmitted through the spindle to a network of suction grooves, bounded by EPDM O-rings, designed for optimal sealing compression. The more flexible EPDM reduces surface marking and ensures a durable seal thanks to its excellent resilience [7].

The chuck/spindle centring is adjusted (backlash +0/+20 μm), while the workpiece centring has a non-zero minimum backlash (+3/+17 μm), guaranteeing a margin of adjustment for the operator.

Counterbores are fitted under the M12 fixing screws to distribute the fastening pressure over the entire bearing surface, rather than concentrating it under the screw heads. The through holes are sized at $\varnothing 12.2$ mm for M12 screws, positioning the chuck at the right angle.

With a vacuum of 70 mbar (capacity of the rotary union), this final design (Fig. 3.d) generates a clamping force of 347 N.

Fig. 2. Rotating joint leak-tightness test setup. a) Ducts blocked for testing. b) Pneumatic assembly incorporating the TPR280 gauge

Fig. 3. Chuck design. a) Spider grid. b) Universal plate. c) Made-to-measure one-piece. d) Final design of the vacuum chuck.

2.5 ANSYS numerical simulations

The abundance of suction grooves and seals drastically reduced the contact surface between the part and the chuck. A quick calculation showed that the theoretical surface pressure (0.38 MPa) was acceptable, but it was decided to study the distribution of this surface pressure using a Static Structural model on ANSYS (Fig. 4.a) to check that even in the case of stress concentrations, the induced deformations remained acceptable.

Stress concentrations on certain edges do not exceed 2.56% of the yield strength of C10100 H02 copper (69 MPa). No plastic deformation will then be caused by clamping. The machined surface will only be elastically deformed by a maximum of 34.8 nanometres along the axis of the part (Fig. 4.b), i.e. 1.7% of the allocated flatness tolerance of 2 μm .

2.6 Adjustment and safety elements

It is important to monitor the vacuum in the system to prevent the part from coming off during the operation (leak, problem with the vacuum unit, etc.). Thanks to an electronic management system, the programme will be blocked until a sufficient vacuum is reached, and if this threshold is exceeded during machining, an emergency stop will be automatically triggered. There will also be a function for controlled reduction of the clamping force, enabling the operator to adjust the workpiece. A workpiece release function has also been included. A proposed electrical diagram has been drawn up, pending validation by the relevant departments at CERN and the machine tool manufacturer.

2.7 Manufacturing the system

The primary part was manufactured in EN-AW 6082 (T6) on the Mikroturm 100 lathe. The milling of the grooves was programmed using WorkNC software. To finish the interface with the accelerator disc using a diamond tool, the chuck was mounted and adjusted directly on the spindle.

A metrological check was carried out on the main functional links. Some tolerances of the short centring positioning the chuck on the spindle are not respected, in the order of a micrometer, but this does not compromise installation or use. The interface with the accelerator disc conforms perfectly to the definition drawing.

2.8 Tests

The clamping force was measured at 70 mbar using a dedicated test bench (Fig. 4.c). A simulated workpiece was made, so that a basket could be suspended from it. By adding material to the basket, the weight that can be supported by the chuck (and therefore its clamping force) can be measured [8].

Using a simulated workpiece with a surface finish of Ra 0.8, a force of 248 N was obtained. The difference from the theoretical calculations is explained by the contact between the part and the chuck, which eliminates an area subject to the effects of vacuum [9]. Then, the part was reworked to bring it to Ra 3.2, to degrade the contact between the surfaces, but the clamping force changed only slightly (254 N). In both cases, a force more than 13 times greater than required according to theoretical calculations (18.4 N) was obtained.

The system was installed on the Mikroturm 100 lathe for validation in real-use conditions (Fig. 4.d). Assembly and adjustment took less than 30 minutes. On activation, clamping is immediate, and maximum vacuum is reached in a matter of seconds. Although the part was firmly held, no machining test was carried out for safety reasons (no electronic management system).

Fig. 4. Different tests on the final design. a) Surface pressure on the workpiece during clamping. b) Elastic deformation of the machined face during clamping. c) Clamping force evaluation facility. d) Disc clamped by the vacuum chuck on the lathe.

3. Technical conclusions

The project involved the development of a vacuum clamping system for the finish machining of copper parts on high-precision lathes. The one-piece chuck designed meets the requirements of the specifications: jaw-free holding, resistance to cutting forces and compatibility with dimensional and geometric tolerances. ANSYS simulations confirmed that the clamping pressure did not induce any significant deformation, despite the presence of numerous grooves. Vacuum adhesion analysis showed a significant safety margin with respect to cutting forces, validating the robustness of the system.

Direct manufacture on the Mikroturn 100 enabled the required tolerances to be achieved, verified by a partial but representative metrological inspection. The use of standard materials, components available in the workshop and the production of full documentation (drawings, range, protocols) made it easy to demonstrate the feasibility and correct operation of the system.

4. Future work

To finalise the project, a joint validation with the design office in charge of the safety protocols will be necessary, to optimise the electronic part before commissioning.

Ordering EPDM O-rings directly to the groove diameters would be a judicious choice, as the installation of the O-ring has proved difficult, particularly around the small-diameter grooves.

An improvement in sealing is also possible. By replacing the rotary union and the Festo connections [10], it would be possible to achieve 0.5 mbar (the limit of the vacuum unit), which would increase the clamping force by 7.6% [2], without any significant impact on disc deformation.

References

- [1] D. GLAUDE, Optical analysis of the roughness of a Cl-astnd0185 electrode
- [2] K.R. Rajagopal, Remarks on the notion of “pressure” (2015)
- [3] G. Kudra, J. Awrejcewicz, A smooth model of the resultant friction force on a plane contact area (2015)
- [4] B.W.L.M. Sessink *, N.F. Verster Design of elastomer O-ring vacuum seals (1973)
- [5] Niederhauser, PML-PAL chuck documentation « Chapitre 7 » <https://www.niederhauser.ch/fr/produits/man-drin-pneumatique-de-precisi>
- [6] B. Denkena, D. Dahlmann, N. Sassi, The Finite Element Analysis of High Precision Positioning System (2018)
- [7] Kastrade, “EPDM Rubber Gasket Technical Information” <https://www.kastrade.com/p/epdm-rubber-gaskets-technical-information>
- [8] M. Ismisafwan, M. Gan Jet Hong, C. Bih-Lii, Determination of static friction coefficient of a material using clamp method (2024)
- [9] P. Liu, H. Zhao, K. Huang, Q. Chen, Research on normal contact stiffness of rough surface considering friction based on fractal theory (2015)
- [10] Festo, « Multiple distributor QSLV, QST, QSQ » https://www.festo.com/media/catalog/246593_documentation.pdf